

BA'ZI TO'RTINCHI DARAJALI TENGLAMALARNI YECHISHDA O'ZGARUVCHILARNI ALMASHTIRISH USULIDAN FOYDALANISH.

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Agar

$$F(f(x)) = 0 \quad (1)$$

tenglama berilgan bo'lsa, uni $y = f(x)$ almashtirish yordamida

$$F(y) = 0 \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishga keltiriladi. Shundan so'ng, (2) tenglamaning hamma $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n, \dots$ yechimlarini topib, quyidagi tenglamalar majmuasini yechishga keltiriladi.

$$f(x) = y_1, \quad f(x) = y_2, \quad \dots, \quad f(x) = y_n, \dots \quad (3)$$

Biz (1) ko'rinishdagi to'rtinchi darajali tenglamalarning turli xususiy hollari uchun o'zgaruvchilarni almashtirish usullarini ko'rib o'tamiz.

1. $(x - \alpha)(x - \beta)(x - \gamma)(x - \delta) = A$ ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni yechish.

$$(x - \alpha)(x - \beta)(x - \gamma)(x - \delta) = A \quad (4)$$

bunda $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ va A lar uchun $\alpha < \beta < \gamma < \delta$ va $\beta - \alpha = \delta - \gamma$ shartlar o'rinli bo'lsa

$$y = \frac{x - \alpha + x - \beta + x - \gamma + x - \delta}{4}$$

almashtirish bajarib bikvadrat tenglamani yechishga keltiriladi.

1-misol. Ushbu

$$(x + 1)(x + 2)(x + 4)(x + 5) = 0 \quad (5)$$

tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. $y = \frac{x + 1 + x + 2 + x + 4 + x + 5}{4}$

$y = x + 3$ yoki $x = y - 3$ almashtirish bajarib (5) tenglamani

$$(y - 2)(y - 1)(y + 1)(y + 2) = 10$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin.

$$(y^2 - 4)(y^2 - 1) = 10 \quad (6)$$

Bu bikvadrat tenglama 2 ta ildizga ega. $y_1 = \sqrt{6}$ va $y_2 = -\sqrt{6}$.

Natijada (5) tenglama 2 ta ildizga ega.

$$x_1 = -\sqrt{6} - 3; \quad x_2 = \sqrt{6} - 3$$

Javob: $x_1 = -\sqrt{6} - 3$; $x_2 = \sqrt{6} - 3$

2. $(ax^2 + b_1x + c)(ax^2 + b_2x + c) = Ax^2$ ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni yechish.

$$(ax^2 + b_1x + c)(ax^2 + b_2x + c) = Ax^2 \quad (7)$$

bunda $c \neq 0$ va $A \neq 0$, $x = 0$ ildizga ega emas, shuning uchun (7) tenglamaning har 2 tomonini x^2 ga bo'lib unga teng kuchli

$$\left(ax + \frac{c}{x} + b_1\right)\left(ax + \frac{c}{x} + b_2\right) - A = 0$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. $y = ax + \frac{c}{x}$ almashtirish bajarib kvadrat tenglamani yechishga keltiriladi.

2-misol. Ushbu

$$(x^2 + x + 2)(x^2 + 2x + 2) = 2x^2 \quad (8)$$

tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. $x = 0$ (8) tenglamaning ildizi bo'lmaydi, shuning uchun uni x^2 ga bo'lib unga teng kuchli

$$\left(x + 1 + \frac{2}{x}\right)\left(x + 2 + \frac{2}{x}\right) = 2$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. $y = x + \frac{2}{x}$ almashtirish bajarib $(y + 1)(y + 2) = 2$ tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

Bundan $y_1 = 0$ va $y_2 = -3$. Natijada berilgan (8) tenglama quyidagi $x + \frac{2}{x} = 0$ va $x + \frac{2}{x} = -3$ tenglamalar majmuasiga teng kuchli. Bu birlashma 2 ta $x_1 = -1$ va $x_2 = -2$ ildizga ega.

Javob: $x_1 = -1$, $x_2 = -2$.

3. $(x - \alpha)(x - \beta)(x - \gamma)(x - \delta) = Ax^2$ ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni yechish.

$$(x - \alpha)(x - \beta)(x - \gamma)(x - \delta) = Ax^2 \quad (9)$$

bunda $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ va A lar shundayki, $\alpha\beta = \gamma\delta \neq 0$. Birinchi qavsni ikkinchisiga, uchinchi qavsni to'rtinchisiga ko'paytirib $(x^2 - x(\alpha + \beta) + \alpha\beta)(x^2 - x(\gamma + \delta) + \gamma\delta) = Ax^2$ ni hosil

qilamiz. Endi (9) tenglamani (7) ko'rinishda yozish va yechish mumkin.

3-misol. Ushbu

$$(x - 2)(x - 1)(x - 8)(x - 4) = 7x^2 \quad (10)$$

tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. $[(x - 2)(x - 4)][(x - 1)(x - 8)] = 7x^2$

$$(x^2 - 6x + 8)(x^2 - 9x + 8) = 7x^2$$

$x = 0$ tenglamaning ildizi bo'lmaganligi uchun uni x^2 ga bo'lamiz va unga teng kuchli tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\left(x - 6 + \frac{8}{x}\right)\left(x - 9 + \frac{8}{x}\right) = 7$$

$x + \frac{8}{x} = y$ deb almashtirish bajarib $(y - 6)(y - 9) = 7$ kvadrat tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$y_1 = \frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2} \text{ va } y_2 = \frac{15 - \sqrt{37}}{2}$$

Natijada (10) tenglama quyidagi tenglamalar majmuasiga teng kuchli.

$$x + \frac{8}{x} = \frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2}; \quad x + \frac{8}{x} = \frac{15 - \sqrt{37}}{2}$$

Bu birlamaning birinchi tenglamasi yechimi

$$x_1 = \frac{\frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2}\right)^2 - 32}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{\frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{15 + \sqrt{37}}{2}\right)^2 - 32}}{2},$$

Birlashmaning 2-tenglamasi yechimga ega emas. Demak, berilgan tenglama 2 ta ildizga ega

$$\text{Javob: } x_1 = \frac{15 + \sqrt{37} + \sqrt{30\sqrt{37} + 134}}{4}, \quad x_2 = \frac{15 + \sqrt{37} - \sqrt{30\sqrt{37} + 134}}{4}.$$

4. Ushbu

$$a(cx^2 + p_1x + q)^2 + b(cx^2 + p_2x + q)^2 = Ax^2$$

ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni yechish.

$$a(cx^2 + p_1x + q)^2 + b(cx^2 + p_2x + q)^2 = Ax^2 \quad (11)$$

bunda a, b, c, q, A sonlar, $q \neq 0, A \neq 0, c \neq 0, b \neq 0$.

$x = 0$ ildizga ega emas. Shuning uchun (11) tenglamani x^2 ga bo'lib unga teng kuchli

$$a\left(cx + \frac{q}{x} + p_1\right)^2 + b\left(cx + \frac{q}{x} + p_2\right)^2 = A$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. $y = cx + \frac{q}{x}$ almashtirish bajarib kvadrat tenglamani yechishga keltiriladi.

4-misol. Ushbu

$$3(x^2 + 2x - 1)^2 - 2(x^2 + 3x - 1)^2 + 5x^2 = 0 \quad (12)$$

tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. $x = 0$ (12) tenglamaning ildizi bo'lmaganligi uchun har ikki tomonini x^2 ga bo'lib,

$$3\left(x + 2 - \frac{1}{x}\right)^2 - 2\left(x + 3 - \frac{1}{x}\right)^2 + 5 = 0 \quad (13)$$

(12) tenglamaga teng kuchli tenglamani hosil qilamiz. $x - \frac{1}{x} = y$ almashtirish bajarib (13) tenglamani

$$3(y + 2)^2 - 2(y + 3)^2 + 5 = 0 \quad (14)$$

ko'rinishda yozamiz. (14) kvadrat tenglama 2 ta $y_1 = 1$, $y_2 = -1$ ildizga ega.

Shuning uchun (13) tenglama quyidagi tenglamalar majmuasiga teng kuchli.

$$x - \frac{1}{x} = 1 \text{ va } x - \frac{1}{x} = -1 \quad (15)$$

(15) tenglamalar majmuasi to'rtta ildizga ega.

$$x_1 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_3 = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_4 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

Bular (15) tenglamaning ildizlari bo'ladi.

$$\text{Javob: } x_1 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_3 = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_4 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

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